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Utilization of Virtual and Non-Virtual Classrooms for Learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the Utilization of virtual and Non-virtual classrooms in learning of Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State. Four objectives, research questions and hypotheses guided the study. A Descriptive survey design was used for the study. The Population comprised of 165 final year students. The entire population was used for the study. There was no sampling. Data for the study were collected with a questionnaire. Test-retest method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument which yielded a coefficient value of 0.84. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to analyze the hypotheses. The findings revealed that zoom and videoconferencing as part of virtual classrooms were not utilized for learning Business Education courses while student-teacher physical interaction and student-student interaction was utilized for learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State. Based on the findings, conclusions were made. This researcher recommended that resource person in the programme should also adopt other types of classes than stick to the non-virtual.

Keywords: Virtual and Non-virtual Classroom, Teaching and Learning, zoom, video conference,

INTRODUCTION

Learning is part of human existence. Each day of a man's life, he learns new things to survive in a changing world. Because man is a social being, he interacts with his environment at any stage in time and learns new things. In fact, learning starts from the informal (home) in a cradle format, continues or progresses to the school, college, university, workplace (Singh, 2011). With the advent of more technologies, the teaching and learning process is breaking out of the narrow box that it was trapped in during the 20th century: teachers' professionalism, reflection, ingenuity and technology are pushing learning to a very exciting stage where the new generation can easily connect to the teacher through a mobile or viral classroom.

Business Education is concerned with education that seeks to educate individuals for and about business. It is an aspect of educational programme offered at the higher institutions of learning, which prepares students for careers in business. Obanya (2012) sees Business Education as that aspect of vocational education programmes which prepares individuals for gainful employment through acquisition of skills and knowledge that effect the business world. According to Ubulom (2010), Business Education is the transfer of pedagogical and business competencies necessary for teaching business attitudes, concepts, skills and knowledge. He further stated that it can be seen as an aspect of educational or training process which an individual receives with the primary motive of enabling him acquire adequate attitudes, concepts, knowledge, understanding and skills in.

Virtual classroom is an online learning environment in which the learners and instructors interact together. This definition was buttressed by Finkelstein (2006) who described virtual classroom as a visual contact between participants and instructor in an online environment as if they are engaged in face-to-face classroom setting. It

is an environment located within a computer mediated communication system for instruction to take place (Rajnish & Swati, 2013). Some features and compositions that make virtual classroom essential in teaching and learning processes are Assignments folders, Audio features, Blog, Chat room, Video component, Simulation tools, Grading books, Emails, Online calendars, Examinations and Quizzes (Obasa & Mbing, 2010; Yang & Liu, 2017). Virtual environments are considered suitable in teaching and learning of science-based subjects (Barbour & Reeves, 2019; Falode, 2014). In a virtual classroom setting, the learners actively engage in synchronous instruction meaning that the teacher and learners are logged into the classroom at the same time just like in a real-world conventional classroom system.

Virtual classroom has been found to be very effective in the dispensation of Distance Education Programme in many countries of the world. The strategy has been extended as a veritable tool in enhancing teaching and learning in a diversified form of education. Virtual classroom, generally, is appreciated by students as a result of the abundant resources and free time it allows as well as autonomous study, intuitive knowledge and selective contents (Falloon, 2012). Students must arrive on time, and when he/she enters into the classroom, he/she find a fixed classroom with teachers, fellow learners, a whiteboard, LCD projector, optionally a television screen with audio and video facility (Hall, 2012). Mallareddy (2013) investigated the use virtual classroom in Telugu Language teaching and noted that it was advantageous in removing the barriers of time and space, overcoming the unavailability of teachers; sessions can be recorded quicker to organize. However, there was lack of tools and technology, lack of interaction with learners. Gedera (2014) in an attempt to develop a better understanding of students' experiences of learning with the specific online learning technology of Adobe Connect virtual classroom discovered that students were satisfied with the platform of learning. Utilization is the act of making use of certain things for a purpose. It is also seen as making use of Resources for the purpose of attaining educational goals. Olagunju and Abiola (2018) states that utilization of resources in the teaching brings about fruitful learning since it stimulates students sense as well as motivating them. Adegboyeje (2010) stated that, utilization is the degree or extent to which an item has been put into effective use. According to Adegboyeje, various degrees of utilization include non-utilization, underutilization, maximum utilization, optimum utilization and overutilization. Utilization amounts to making use of something or somebody, especially for a practical purpose. It may amount to doing something with a machine, a method, an entity, for a particular purpose. It is simply the act of using something in order to achieve a set goal. Operationally, utilization refers to the act of making practical and effective use of something, especially for a particular purpose.

Non-virtual view is a very task oriented style, but virtual view is much more open ended project style, the difficulty is in the mind set. Have a task, compete a task (Benbunan-Fich, & Hilts, 2013). Non-virtual learning takes place exactly how it sounds, i.e. non virtually. Skill and behavior is taught, practiced and considerable time acquiring information and learning new skills.

Non-virtual classroom takes place exactly how it sounds, that is, non-virtually, skills and behavior are taught. It's also a traditional way of teaching or face to face method of teaching. Traditional classroom (Non-virtual) has its own campus and fixed classrooms students neither have near the college or on the campus. They attend classes every day and follow the same curriculum.

A traditional classroom (Non-virtual) involves a standard curriculum delivered by a teacher in person. Standardized tools are administered at regular intervals to test student's comprehension. This model is where students time, place and pace of learning remains constant. Non-virtual classroom (traditional classroom) is here a teacher moderates and regulates the flow of information and knowledge students are expressed to continue developing their knowledge of subjects outside of school through homework exercise. Here, student's main resources their instructor who only teachers them face-to-face. While the virtual classroom is the opposite. A classroom is a place or room that enable teachers to send assignments, make announcements and conduct questions and answers. The style, size or type can be an enhancement to teaching and learning, hence 'en.wikipedia.org/wiki/classroom' deduction that the size, interior areas, colors, type or furniture and flooring are very vital in the preparation of a place/room as classroom. Virtual Learning is an e-learning concept whose definition and prime objective is to enable the teachers and the students to impart and perceive education online, principally over the Internet. It also allows teachers and students to communicate, interact and, work

together with one another remotely from any location, without actually being physically present face-to-face, through, You Tube, Facebook, Zoom, Free Conference, Webinars, Audio and Video conferences, Web Presentations, Live streaming, Text chats, Learning Management System (LMS) and online training courses (www.edusys.co, 2020). The creation of the virtual classroom has made it possible for learners to harness the features of the Internet to create meaningful and constructivist learning environments (Gabriel, 2014). In this regard, physical classroom features have been transferred into a virtual classroom with enhanced features. Unlike a physical classroom, a virtual classroom is learner-centred. It gives the learners the flexibility of attendance at their convenience. The features that are prevalent in the virtual classroom include tools such as the online calendars, online help guides, online grading books, examinations and quizzes as well as emails, instant messages, chat rooms, discussion boards and file transfers. It supports active learning by providing an environment with the learning tools, learning materials, and opportunities for contextual discussion (Yang & Liu, 2017). This allows the learners to engage in learning activities by more than simply reading through the contents provided in the virtual classroom (Phillips, 2015).

Business education is one of the vocational courses taught in academic institutions in Nigeria. According to Imeokparia and Ediagbonya (2014), Business education is described as an aspect of education that is geared at equipping the learners (students) with business and education competencies (that is, skills, knowledge and attitude) needed to effectively and efficiently function in the world of work either as an employee or an employer (job/wealth creator). Business education is a type of training that is concerned with the achievement of all aims of education at any level of learning with the primary objective of preparing the subject to enter into a business career, to render efficient services therein and to improve their standard of living (Kanu, 2017). This became necessary to Evaluate Utilization of virtual and Non-virtual classrooms in teaching and learning of Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State.

Virtual learning has been part of the integration of the use of technological tools in this digital age and new normal. The formation of a knowledge society and the digital storage of development of modern civilization culture still remain a continuous process in the era of virtual teaching and learning within the education system especially during this global pandemic lockdown. This article reviews the use of virtual teaching and learning as techniques to improve digitalization in the use of new e-tools in teaching and learning in Nigeria. To achieve this, the concept of virtual teaching and learning is reviewed with the intention of looking at its features in digital education. The benefits of virtual teaching and learning are many which include opportunity for timely and distance education, better interactions, easily accessible to learners; the lesson can be easily tracked and recorded.

Virtual classroom offerings place an emphasis on using web conferencing technologies to replicate the core activities, interactions and channels of communication that would occur in a traditional classroom-based environment. Virtual classroom sessions are often called web-based training, webinars, virtual meetings, and web conferencing (Stephens & Mottet, 2018). A virtual classroom is an online learning environment in which students and teachers interact via the technical tools provided by the software. Virtual classroom software is used by educational institutions to host classes remotely while maintaining the functionality available in a traditional classroom environment, Laal, Laal and Kermanshahi (2012). A virtual classroom is an online learning environment that can be web-based and accessed through a portal or software-based and require a downloadable executable file. Just like in a real-world classroom, a student in a virtual classroom participates in synchronous instruction, which means that the teacher and students are logged into the virtual learning environment at the same time (Camacho, Minelli, & Grosseck, 2012). Virtual classrooms are used to apply the multimodality principle to distance learners (Schullo, 2017) who need to have support and guidance, to feel social presence, to share responsibility, and to be motivated by instructors. Virtual classrooms are online environments that enable students and instructors to communicate synchronously, by means of audio, video, text chat, interactive whiteboard, application sharing, instant polling, and other such features, as though they were standing face to face in a classroom (Parker & Martin, 2010). A virtual classroom is similar to a physical classroom in that both allow for immediate feedback, support consensus and decision-making in group activities with 'just-in-time clarification and information,' provide guided pacing and discipline in learning, and foster the development of group cohesion and a sense of community (Schullo, 2017). A virtual classroom holds

real-time lessons remotely while offering the same collaborative tools and level of interaction possible in a physical classroom. Educational institutions utilize virtual classroom software to provide access to students who may not be able to attend in-person courses. Through the virtual classroom environment, teachers can interact with students and students can engage with lesson materials, view presentations and videos, and take tests, all in real time, (Crişan and Enache, 2013).

Virtual learning is an e-learning concept whose definition and prime objective is to enable the teachers and the students to impart and perceive education online, principally over the Internet. It also allows teachers and students to communicate, interact and, work together with one another remotely from any location, without actually being physically present face-to-face, though, You Tube, Facebook, Zoom, Free Conference, Webinars, Audio and Video conferences, Web Presentations, Live streaming, Text chats, Learning Management System (LMS) and online training courses (www.edusys.co, 2020).

Another definition refers virtual teaching and learning system an an online system that allows education materials to be transmitted through the internet and transfer knowledge from organization to employee, or teacher to student. Various examples of virtual teaching and learning include but not limited to Degree Programme, video or audio lecture, webinar etc.

Furthermore, Beek, (2011) stated that virtual learning uses computer software, the Internet or both to deliver instruction to students. This minimizes or eliminates the need for teachers and students to share a classroom. Virtual teaching is a place where teachers are facilitators and students are actively engaged and interacting with one another, this is a place where students are comfortable and safe and still to learn. Teachers make use of all available means of online teaching to teach the students, also make sure that the classroom is interactive. In the classroom, there should be teacher-student interaction, student-teacher interaction and student-student interaction. Virtual learning does not include the increasing use of e-mail or online forums to help teachers better communicate with students and parents about coursework and student progress; as helpful as these learning management systems are, they do not change how students are taught.

Zoom as part of virtual classroom is one of the most mainstream video conferencing answers for organizations. It is highlight rich, with different plans dependent on business size and needs. A zoom session is one of the types of synchronous learning. Synchronous Learning is a modern notion derived from e-learning which focuses on integrating technology with teaching methodologies as a means of delivery within educational institutions for the sake of making the learning process easier for students and teachers. This concept is characterized by a combination of many traits such as a technological device connected to a network (zoom application), a suitable timing for both teachers and students, different locations, real time communication, online participants, and instantaneous feedback through video, voice or text chat interaction between participants. (Hrastinski, 2017). During the zoom session, students may ask questions to help them structure their sentences or do their assignments before posting them; they may be exposed to listening input to increase their schemata that develops their error correction system which is directly linked to conscious learning of a language. At the same time students receive the essential feedback on their work from their teacher and classmates which can decrease the anxiety levels felt when sharing with others (Chen & Lee, 2011).

Video conferencing is also part of virtual classrooms and it is accepted as a learning tool. New technologies, such as video conferencing, have given teachers new ways of presenting materials, working with students, and thus they are stimulating the development of strategies that are consistent with new technology. Video conferencing uses synchronous two-way audio and two-way compressed video through the Internet. Video conferencing students use special cameras, look at monitors and use the microphone of a computer or mobile device at any location. Students receive instructions and information on any topic through video conferencing, and are able to ask questions to participants from all locations involved in the video conference.

Video conferencing has flourished with the development of various services on the Internet. Video conferencing, as a way of open and distance learning, provides education and training in a more flexible way than the regular ones. Video conferencing is defined as interactive and synchronous voice, video and data transfer conducted between two or more points via communication lines (Gough, 2016). This system reduces the cost of education by connecting students and teachers who are in different locations.

Non-virtual classroom are non-digital classrooms where teaching and learning occurs physically in a confined environment or physical structure where the learner physically meets the teacher who is usually the source of information on a subject matter meets with the learners directly, presents the topic to be discussed in a particular course or subject to them, explain and as well give room for them to ask questions on the areas or aspects that are not too clear to them (Ogoh, 2021) This encourages direct participation from the learners who are privileged to see their teacher or resource person physically.

A Non-Virtual classroom comes in various categories such as; physical student-teacher interaction, student-student interaction, student-student collaboration and physical mentorship in a chosen location or address (Ogoh, 2021), Studies shows that most facilitators or resource person in various educational programmes adopt non-virtual classroom as a way of driving the objective of the programmes that they are part of the reasons for this are; it creates an opportunity for the learners to see the teacher, facilitator or resources person physically it allows them to have a direct contact with the study materials from the teacher, or facilitator or resource person who happens to be the source of the study material than incurring extra cost to source for the material (igwe, 2021)

Physical student-lecturer interaction as part of non-virtual classroom in type of classroom that is designed or arranged in a way that students who are the learners and recipients can have a one-on-one direct contact and interaction with their teacher who is charged with the responsibility of teaching the students and ensuring that they understand the contents of the subject matter being discussed in the teaching and learning session (Igwe, 2021). Some of the benefits and the reasons why most resource persons, teachers, facilitators and programme opt for student-teacher interaction are: it helps the teacher to explain the concepts directly to the students, it helps the students to ask the teacher questions directly for clarification on areas that are confusing in the course or subject, it saves cost, it helps to reduce the amount of time spent in sourcing for materials virtually, it brings the teacher close to the students and also brings the learners (students) close to the teacher as well (Ogoh, 2021). This has a higher advantage over virtual classroom because it is not affected by network or any challenge from network or service providers, it does not have anything to do with power supply or power outage or interruption because it is always in use even without a corresponding power supply (Igwe, 2021)

Student-student interaction as part of non-virtual classroom in today's society and learning environment. This is also referred to as student-student collaboration where students meet physically to discuss on issues or a particular topic or topics taught during their physical class section. Some of the advantages of using this part method for learning in various educational programmes is that, it creates room for students to interact with fellow students, given for sharing of ideas amongst learners/students, creates opportunity for learners to learn more from their peers/colleagues, it makes learning easier since its coming from their peer/fellow students, it gives room for shy learners to ask questions and also learn from their fellow learners whom they are easily free to discuss and interact with (Chukwuma, 2020).

Most programmes prefers this to that of virtual-classroom because students have the opportunity of meeting fellow learners physically than virtually (AISHA, 2021).

Statement of the problem

Business Education programme plays significant roles in equipping it trainees with the right skills and aptitudes that will enable them to be self-reliant, employers of labour, employees in various organization and as well function effectively as rational individuals on the society by contributing meaningfully to the advancement of the society through the knowledge and skills acquired in the programme. It is important to note that the contents of the programme has been so designed to achieve this. However, the mode of instruction adopted by the resource persons in this programme also matters a lot because the aim of the teaching or instructional process is to ensure that the goal of programme is achieved. It is on this ground that this study seeks to determine the extent of utilization of virtual and non-virtual classrooms for learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State.

Purpose of the Study

The main aim of this study is to examine the Utilization of virtual and Non-virtual classrooms for learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the extent of utilization of zoom for learning of Business Education courses in Bayelsa State.

2. Examine the extent of utilization of videoconferencing for learning of Business Education courses in Bayelsa State.
3. Examine the extent of utilization of physical students-teacher interaction for learning of Business Education courses in Bayelsa State.
4. Examine the extent of utilization of physical student-student interaction for learning of Business Education courses in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions:

The following research questions guided the study.

1. To what extent is zoom utilized for learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State?
2. To what extent is videoconferencing utilized for learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State?
3. To what extent is physical student-teacher interaction utilized for learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State?
4. To what extent is student-student interaction utilized for learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null are formulated for the study, which will be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the extent zoom is utilized for learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the extent videoconferencing is utilized for learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the extent student-teacher interaction is utilized for learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the extent student-student interaction is utilized for learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State.

METHOD

This study was on utilization of virtual and non-virtual classrooms in learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised of 165 final year students. The entire population was used for the study. Four purposes of the study, four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled "Questionnaire on utilization of virtual and non-virtual classrooms for learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State". The instrument was structured on four-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE) = 4, High Extent (HE) = 3, Low Extent (LE) = 2 and very Low Extent (VLE) =1. Test-retest method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument and a reliability coefficient was obtained 0.82. This shows that instrument was reliable. The copies of the instrument were administered to the respondent with the aid of the course representatives in the departments. Mean and standard deviation were used in analyzing the research questions while t-test was used in testing the hypotheses formulated in the study at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *To what extent is zoom utilized for learning Business Education courses Bayelsa State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Extent of utilization of zoom for learning Business Education Courses

S/N	Items	Male (80)			Female (85)		
		X	SD	RMK	X	SD	RMK
1	zoom are used for academic interaction in classroom.	2.20	0.44	VLE	1.65	0.33	VLE
2	Zoom are used for with setting a clear plan for writing and speaking.	2.04	0.41	VLE	1.48	0.29	VLE
3	Zoom provides quick feedback from the teacher.	2.23	0.45	VLE	1.81	0.36	VLE
4	The use of zoom motivated me to seek help from tutors, classmates, and the instructor	2.44	0.49	VLE	1.96	0.39	VLE
5	The use of zoom helped me participate in the class in ways that enhanced my learning	2.51	0.5	VLE	2.01	0.40	VLE
Total Mean/SD		11.42	2.29		8.91	1.77	
Grand mean/SD		2.28	0.46		1.78	0.35	

Source: Field survey, 2025

The analysis in table 1 shows that all mean responses are at a very low extent which implies that zoom cloud application as part of virtual classroom is not utilized in learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State.

Research Question Two: *To what extent is videoconferencing utilized for learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State?*

Table 2: Mean and standard Deviation on the Extent of utilization of video conferencing for Learning Business Education Courses

S/N	Items	Male (80)			Female (85)		
		X	SD	RMK	X	SD	RMK
6	Video conference offers the possibilities to efficiently manage the time in teaching and learning	2.20	0.44	VLE	1.89	0.38	VLE
7	Video conference encourages students to pursue through information	2.20	0.44	VLE	1.65	0.33	VLE
8	Video conference helps students to carry out their academic tasks more efficiently.	2.27	0.45	VLE	1.92	0.38	VLE
9	Video conference helps students become self- knowledgeable	2.33	0.47	VLE	2.24	0.45	VLE
10	Video conference offers the possibilities to efficiently manage the time in teaching and learning	2.36	0.47	VLE	2.06	0.41	VLE
Total Mean/SD		11.36	2.27		9.76	1.95	
Grand mean/SD		2.27	0.45		1.95	0.39	

Source: Field survey, 2025

The analysis in table 2 shows that all the mean responses are at a very low extent which shows that video conferencing as part of virtual classroom is not utilized in learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State.

Research Question Three. *To what extent is physical student-student interaction utilized for learning business education courses in Bayelsa State?*

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Extent of Utilization of Student-Teacher interaction for Learning Business Education Courses

S/N	Items	Male (80)			Female (85)		
		X	SD	RMK	X	SD	RMK
11	It creates one-one contact with lecturers	3.18	0.64	HE	2.82	0.56	HE
12	It enhances interaction between students and lecturers	3.49	0.69	HE	2.86	0.57	HE
13	It is used to save cost of purchasing materials virtually	3.38	0.68	HE	2.92	0.58	HE
14	It creates room for clearer explanation of concepts	3.40	0.68	HE	2.73	0.55	HE
15	It gives room for learners to ask questions directly	3.39	0.68	HE	2.76	0.55	HE
Total Mean/SD		16.84	3.37		14.09	2.81	
Grand mean/SD		3.37	0.67		2.82	0.56	

Source: Field survey, 2025

The analysis in table 3 shows that all the mean responses are at a high extent which shows that student teacher physical interaction as part of Non-Virtual classroom is utilized in learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State.

Research Question Four: *To what extent is physical student-students interaction utilized for learning business education courses in Bayelsa State?*

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Extent of Utilization of Student physical interaction for Learning Business Education Course

S/N	Items	Male (80)			Female (85)		
		X	SD	RMK	X	SD	RMK
16	It creates room for student-student interaction	3.15	0.70	HE	2.87	0.57	HE
17	It creates opportunity for learners to learn from their colleagues	3.40	0.68	HE	2.76	0.55	HE
18	It provides a platform for shy learners to ask questions from other learners	3.33	0.67	HE	2.90	0.58	HE
19	It makes learning easier for learners	3.40	0.68	HE	2.71	0.54	HE
20	It gives opportunity for group discussions	3.44	0.69	HE	2.78	0.56	HE
Total Mean/SD		17.08	3.42		14.02	2.80	
Grand mean/SD		3.42	0.68		2.80	0.56	

Source: Field survey, 2025

The analysis in table 4 shows that all the mean responses are at a high extent. This indicates that student-student physical interaction as part of Non-virtual classroom is utilized for learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the extent Zoom is utilized for learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State.

Table 5: T-test of difference in the Mean Rating of Male and Female respondents on the extent Zoom is utilized for learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State

Respondents	N	X	SD	DF	t-cal	t-crit	Level of Sign.	Decision
Male	80	2.28	0.46	163	8.3	1.960	0.05	Rejected
Female	85	1.78	0.35					

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis in table 5 shows that the t-cal is greater than the t-critical. Hence, the hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean rating of male and female respondents on the extent zoom is utilized for learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the extent video conferencing is utilized for learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State.

Table 6: T-test of difference in the mean rating of male and female respondents on the extent video conferencing is utilized for learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State

Respondents	N	X	SD	DF	t-cal	t-crit	Level of Sign.	Decision
Male	80	2.27	0.45	163	4.6	1.960	0.05	Rejected
Female	85	1.95	0.39					

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis in table 6 shows that the t-cal is greater than the t-crit. Hence the hypotheses was rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the extent they utilize video conferencing for learning in Bayelsa State

Hypotheses 3: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the extent student-teacher interaction for learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State.

Table 7: T-test of Difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the extent students-teacher interaction is utilized for learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State.

Respondents	N	X	SD	DF	t-cal	t-crit	Level of Sign.	Decision
Male	80	3.37	0.67	163	5.5	1.960	0.05	Rejected
Female	85	2.80	0.50					

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis in table 7 shows that the t-cal is higher than the t-critical. Hence, the hypotheses was rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the extent students-teacher interaction is utilized for learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the extent student-student interaction for learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State.

Table 8: T-test of difference in the mean rating of male and female respondents on the extent student-student physical interaction is utilized for learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State

Respondents	N	X	SD	DF	t-cal	t-crit	Level of Sign.	Decision
Male	80	3.42	0.68	163	6.2	1.960	0.05	Rejected
Female	85	2.80	0.56					

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The analysis in table 8 shows that the t-cal is greater than the t-critical. Hence, the hypotheses was rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean rating of male and female respondents on the extent student-student physical interaction is utilized for learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings in table 1 shows that zoom cloud application is very lowly utilized in learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State. This finding is in agreement with the view of Igwe (2021) that some of the reasons for not adopting virtual classroom is due to poor power supply, power outage, power interruption, network issues and challenges and high cost of purchasing the facilities that are used in virtual classroom.

The findings in table 2 shows that video conferencing as part of virtual classroom is not utilized for learning Business Education Courses in Bayelsa State. This findings is in agreement with the view of Igwe (2021) who opined that virtual classrooms of whatever type is faced with the following issues; poor power supply, high cost of equipment's needed for virtual classroom, network issues and constant power outage.

The analysis in table 3 shows that student teacher interaction as part of non-virtual classroom is utilized for learning non-virtual classroom is utilized for learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State. This finding is in agreement with the view of Ogoh (2021) who opined that student-teacher interaction as part of non-virtual classroom helps the teacher to explain the concepts directly to the learners, creates room for learners to ask questions directly from the teacher, and helps to reduce the amount of time spent in sourcing for materials virtually.

The finding in table 4 shows that students interaction as part of non-virtual classroom is utilized learning Business Education courses in Bayelsa State.

This finding is in agreement with the view of Chukwuma (2020) who opined that student- students interaction as part of non-virtual classroom does the following, it creates room students to learn from fellow students, creates opportunities for learners to learn more from their colleagues, creates room from sharing of information/ideas amongst learners.

CONCLUSION

The study was aimed at assessing the utilization of virtual and non-virtual classrooms in learning Business Education comes in Bayelsa State. The aspects of virtual classroom considered were; Zoom and video conferencing while that of the non-virtual was; student-teacher interaction and student-student interaction.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendation were made by the researcher

- a. The facilities needed for zoom cloud application to be utilized should be provided by the bodies in charge.
- b. The facilities needed for video conferencing should be provided by the bodies in charge..
- c. Resource persons in the programme should include virtual classroom

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